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A Case Study On Content Moderation Techniques Employed By Gen AI Chatbots & Its Implications In The Digital Space

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ABSTRACT

The research paper reviews several content moderation techniques on various sensitive socio-political issues present around the world, explicit content against women and children utilised by several AI models like ChatGPT, Google Gemini, and Claude, the reasons behind it, and how some jailbreaks still happen, with real instances and case studies, in addition to concrete measures taken by their companies to promote a safe cyber space. Also, the research also delves into how such content moderation techniques are utilized by some AI models like DeepSeek to deliver responses in tandem with their ruling government in China and how the AI model Grok took the concept of ‘free speech’ too far. Therefore, the paper adopts a case-study approach in reviewing the same.

Keywords: Gen AI Models, Content Moderation, Jailbreaking, Socio-Political Issues, Cybersecurity, Censorship

1. Introduction

1.1. What is Artificial Intelligence?

Artificial Intelligence is a type of technology that allows computers to simulate human cognitive abilities, (i.e) the ability to think and observe like humans from its surroundings, that has been possible through its rigorous training of multiple datasets fed by scientists and tech experts, to enable the computers to analyse a situation and deliver accurate responses, in addition to providing suggestions for future as well. The term ‘Artificial Intelligence’ was coined by the American scientist-John McCarthy in the year 1956 during a computer seminar proposal conducted by Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence.

Artificial Intelligence has been classified into three parts:

- **Artificial Narrow Intelligence:** Most common usage of AI that exists in society, which is used for text generation, driving cars, playing brain games, etc. It is also known as ‘weak AI’.
- **Artificial General Intelligence:** It is a theoretical concept wherein the machine or the computer possess equal cognitive abilities as of a human and excel in every field.
- **Artificial Super Intelligence:** It is also a theoretical concept wherein it has been predicted that the machines and computers can even surpass human thinking and cognition.

Nowadays, AI have become an integral part in every field, where it has been used across all fields, even in personal life in the form of chatbot digital assistants, voice recognition assistants, and usage for software development, cybersecurity, navigation, content personalisation, and even for content creation in the form of Generative AI.

1.2. An Overview of Generative AI

Generative AI, one of AI subsets, creates new content, like text, images, video and codes from simple prompts. Unlike the traditional AI that just answers questions based on the users’ queries, Generative AI has the ability to create new content based on the trained datasets and the users’ wishes, thanks to Large Language Models (LLM) for recognising texts, and neural network architecture technologies such as Transformers (for word processing) and Diffusion Models (for multimedia generation), and prompt engineering, that are used to create new multimedia content based on the users’ keyword inputs.

For ease of use, many AI chatbots found in the mainstream market like ChatGPT, Claude, Google Gemini have built-in Gen AI models to generate such type of content for free or for certain plan

amounts, that has gained traction in industries like Information Technology (IT), Digital Marketing, and Education, for software development, copywriting, graphic design, website design, multimedia production, teaching, notes generation, assignment writing, and essay writing.

Despite its pathbreaking achievements of generating hours of new content in less than a minute from a single sentence or prompt, it has its drawbacks, wherein Gen AI tools can ‘hallucinate’ (i.e.) justify and state confidently inaccurate information, in addition to causing copyright concerns while generating content.

1.3. Importance Of Content Moderation

Content moderation is the process of reviewing and managing user-generated content (text, and multimedia) to ensure that they adhere to the legal framework, the platform’s regulations, and community rules and standards, in order to provide a safe cyber space. It mostly regulates content that depict violence, explicit sexual content, terrorism, hate speech, harassment, and copyright infringement found in the users’ responses delivered by the AI models like ChatGPT, by monitoring the trained data, in addition to the users’ prompts and human feedback.

It is usually done by the AI models to prevent the misuse of AI to create explicit and anti-social content and to protect the users from any harmful content.

2. Review Of Literature

In the era of AI-induced information, even advanced AI models like ChatGPT ‘hallucinate’ and provide misinformation, wherein *D. Naik et.al (2024)* reviewed the limitations of Generative A.I. 's LLM & L.M.M, by discovering its lack of intellectual & emotional intelligence, lack of accuracy in solving mathematical equations, providing misinformation, & violating ethics. However, some sensitive socio-political users’ queries and inputs were monitored by the AI models where *A. Urman & M. Makhortykh (2023)* conducted a comparative analysis of 5 LLM based tools-ChatGPT, Bing Chat/Copilot and Bard/Gemini, on outputs of politics-related prompts, which was concluded that false information dissemination was rampant and with guardrails built to the LLM tools can lead to political information being censored. But such censorship content moderation techniques used by AI models often adhere to the country’s ruling government and their policies, which was observed in many Chinese AI models, including the latest open-source model-DeepSeek R-1. Many researchers like *Y. Xu (2018)* employed technographic inquiry of two

Chinese A.I. chatbots-Xiao Bing and BabyQ on their popular social media platform-WeChat, who concluded that the chatbots provided ambiguous responses to queries regarding politically sensitive topics. Also, *V.P.R. Kumar (2025)* examined the role of DeepSeek A.I., in the context of information seeking behaviour, who concluded that despite transforming information seeking behaviour, it has ‘algorithmic bias’ and can create ‘filter bubbles’ with users exposed to content aligned to their beliefs. In addition to political information, content moderation with regard to explicit content have also been reviewed by researchers like *Martino Pirella* tested six popular AI models with the same explicit input prompt and discovered that the AI models responded in three ways-provided, not provided, and redirection. They later concluded that the collection of personal user data and the tracking of users’ data is more dangerous than the sexual content itself, and how AI companies are redefining content moderation, and privacy.

3. Research Design

3.1. Research Methodology

The paper adopts qualitative research methodology, by employing the case study method for reviewing the various AI models’ content moderation techniques when asked about sensitive socio-political issues and its stance towards explicit and harmful content. The researcher has also collected secondary data by reading news reports and research articles regarding the same.

3.3. Research Objectives

1. To review the LLM models’ content moderation policies and safety techniques utilised by them.
2. To compare the different models’ responses for sensitive content.
3. To analyse cases of over-moderation and under-moderation by some AI models for certain users’ queries.

4. Analysis

4.1. A Deep-Dive Into How AI Models Undertake Content Moderation

Most AI models have two types of content moderation-input and output moderation, where datasets are often segregated during training itself and user prompts that depict harmful, and

explicit content. Also, AI models adopt human feedback techniques such as Reinforcement Learning From Human Feedback (RLHF), to deliver safe and accurate responses. In addition to such training, many researchers do jailbreak prompts and feed manipulative orders to try to intentionally bypass the AI models' security mechanisms, through the process of adversarial testing and red teaming.

However, a new approach has been followed by Anthropic company's AI model-Claude, which has its own set of ethical principles called the Constitutional AI, where it reduces its dependence on human feedback and supervision.

4.2. Comparative Analysis Of How Different AI Models Responses To Sensitive Socio-Political Issues

4.2.1. Explicit Content Against Women And Children

Popular AI models-ChatGPT, and Gemini mostly rely on human feedback, policy filtering and enforcement, automated safety classifiers, where it often follows a more precautionary approach to refuse such users' inputs to minimise risks. Whereas, Claude has its own Constitutional AI, and is very strict when handling such queries related to explicit content. However, Grok has a more permissive philosophy of content moderation (i.e.) it prioritises more on user freedom and less censorship, which delivered a negative impact, wherein multiple investigations revealed that Grok could edit women and children photographs to sexualised content in late 2025, by compiling with the users' responses like 'undress' or 'put here in a bikini'. It garnered strong criticisms from several countries including The European Commission and India and a case was also filed against Grok AI's company-xAI.

4.2.2. Sensitive Political Issues And History Around The World

Since the dawn of civilization, there has been countless conquests, triumphs, loss of innocent lives, and mostly different perspectives of many sensitive political issues around the world, like rise of Hitler, Genocide of Jews, World Wars, India-Pakistan conflict, issue of Taiwan, Israel-Palestine conflict, the 9/11 Twin Tower Attacks, and many more world-altering events, that changed the course of our world and divided people into different thoughts, and ideologies. With Generative AI chatbots emerging as a highly efficient and effective tool for primary cognitive and creative tasks, according to a 2026 study of a German institution, it has the ability to research and present

any specific historical information, according to the users' requests. To quote the proverb, 'History is written by winners', it is often stated that only winners of wars and power-wielding countries showcased one-sided narratives of historical encounters, which is often biased and lessens the sufferings of the defeated citizens, and also the physical literature left behind often trumpeted the ruling parties' viewpoints and ideologies, leaving behind less room for another perspective and thoughts.

With the advent of AI, the emphasis on the models providing neutral information has gained traction, where they have the ability to perform multi-perspective synthesis, wherein they can compare and provide evidence of different writings of the same historic event, by giving two different perspectives in a neutral manner. This method is often followed by AI models like ChatGPT, Claude, and Gemini, by providing a more neutral approach, (i.e.) providing information from all sides. But, two other AI models-Grok and DeepSeek practice a different approach. Grok's parent company often relies on open discussions and less restrictions on sensitive issues that provide less filtered and more direct responses and DeepSeek R-1, which is created by the Chinese company, High Flyer, adhered to their government's policies and often dodges sensitive political topics related to their country like Taiwan or Dalai Lama, with the response: "Sorry, that's beyond my current scope. Let's talk about something else."

4.2.3. Life-Threatening and Self-Harm Related Inputs

As most AI models have content moderation standards based on legal and ethical principles, most AI models refuse to entertain any users' questions to aid for any violent activity against the society, by refusing immediately and suggesting measures to handle things in a non-violent manner. However, if a user asks any questions regarding self-harm or suicide, ChatGPT and Gemini started off with an empathetic response but refusing gently to not aid and later advises the user to contact professional help. However, Grok and DeepSeek refuse outright to not deliver such harmful responses.

4.3. Jailbreaking Lapses That Endanger Content Moderation Policies Of The AI Models

With the advent of advanced AI models' content moderation techniques, that review each and every users' inputs keywords, can be bypassed in a tactful manner, with the process of jailbreaking,

employed by malicious users. Jailbreaking is nothing but bypassing the AI model's safety regulations by manipulation of prompt generation sentences. For example: If a user asks the AI model on how to make an explosive device directly, it will refuse outrightly. However, if the user manipulates it by asking the same instruction for creative purposes (i.e.) for writing a novel or for a movie script, and asking for such content for hypothetical purposes.

But to put guardrails on such jailbreaking attempts, many AI companies have resorted to several cybersecurity methods like Reinforcement Learning From Human Feedback (RLHF), Input and Output Moderation, Red Teaming, Automated Adversarial Training and many more.

5. Conclusion & Scope For Further Research

With AI models here to stay in this digital world, while lending a helpful hand to people from different walks of life, content moderation techniques employed by such models, provide a safe cyberspace in providing ethical, accurate and harmless content, with updating feedback from experts.

India, one of the fastest growing countries in the technological sector can take account of the available LLM models to develop and train its own LLM model, as a helping hand to its citizens, by providing factual and unbiased data, while emerging as a stiff competitor to the available foreign models.

6. Bibliography

Xu, Y. (2018). Programmatic dreams: Technographic inquiry into censorship of Chinese chatbots. *Social Media+ Society*, 4(4), 2056305118808780.

Berger, H., & Shavitt, Y. (2024). Measuring DNS Censorship of Generative AI Platforms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.14286*.

Kuznetsova, E., Makhortykh, M., Vziatysheva, V., Stolze, M., Baghumyan, A., & Urman, A. (2025). In generative AI we trust: can chatbots effectively verify political information?. *Journal of Computational Social Science*, 8(1), 15.

Urman, A., & Makhortykh, M. (2023). The silence of the LLMs: Cross-lingual analysis of political bias and false information prevalence in ChatGPT, Google Bard, and Bing Chat.

Naik, D., Naik, I., & Naik, N. (2024, July). Imperfectly perfect AI chatbots: limitations of generative AI, large language models and large multimodal models. In *The International Conference on Computing, Communication, Cybersecurity & AI* (pp. 43-66). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.

Kumar, P. R. V. (2025). Revolutionizing the Search Game: How Deepseek is Transforming Information-Seeking Behavior in the Digital Age.

Sallam, M., Al-Mahzoum, K., Sallam, M., & Mijwil, M. M. (2025). DeepSeek: Is it the End of Generative AI Monopoly or the Mark of the Impending Doomsday?. *Mesopotamian Journal of Big Data*, 2025, 26-34.

Pirella, Martino, Erotic AI and the Erosion of Safety Standards: A Competitive Analysis of Boundary Management in Large Language Models (November 09, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5726502> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5726502>

7. References

<https://www.tspa.org/curriculum/ts-fundamentals/content-moderation-and-operations/what-is-content-moderation/>

<https://getstream.io/blog/ai-content-moderation/>

<https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/prompt-engineering/>